

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Water Treatment and Child Mortality: A Meta-analysis and Cost-effectiveness Analysis"

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Water Treatment and Child Mortality: A Meta-analysis and Cost-effectiveness Analysis"^[1]. To read these evaluations, please see the links below. The first was a team effort by Hugh Sharma Waddington and Edoardo Masset, who recently published a related systematic review; this evaluation focuses mainly on the meta-analysis and the studies therein. The second (anonymous) evaluation focuses more on the cost-effectiveness analysis. Both evaluators agree that this paper tackles an important question and provides an advance on our prior understanding of the effects of water treatment on child mortality. Both also found areas where the paper could be improved or clarified.

Evaluations and author response

1. [Sharma Waddington and Masset](#)
2. [Anonymous Evaluator 2](#)
3. [Authors' response](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (see footnote)¹

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):² On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Sharma Waddington & Masset	50	2.5
Anonymous evaluator 2	85	3.7

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³ See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.⁴

Evaluation summaries

Sharma Waddington & Masset

We evaluated the conduct, analysis and interpretation of the meta-analysis findings. The paper concerns an important topic for the global burden of infectious disease, particularly in middle-income countries where most of the included studies were conducted. It presents useful information on childhood mortality following water treatment and protection interventions. However, we had major concerns about conduct and reporting, which did not follow systematic review standards of transparency, and we also had major concerns about the interpretation of the findings for policy and research.

Anonymous evaluator 2

1. I do not see any major technical issues with the paper.
2. The paper can be positioned more robustly i.e., the “need for it” needs to be better argued.
3. While the “effect” (mortality reduction) side of the paper has been done well, the “cost” part of the paper could be deepened. This would position it better and be supremely useful to policymakers.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2		
	Sharma Waddington & Masset			Anonymous		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁵	50	(40, 60)	6	85	(75, 95)	7
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁸	80	(70, 90)	9	65	(45, 85)	10

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹¹	50	(40, 60)	12	75	(65, 85)	13
Logic & communication 14	50	(30, 70)	15	95	(90, 100)	
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁶	35	(20, 50)	17	90	(80, 100)	
Real-world relevance ¹⁸	20	(0, 40)	19	50	(25, 75)	20
Relevance to global priorities ²¹	45	(30, 60)	22	90	(85, 95)	23

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2		
	Sharma Waddington & Masset		Anonymous		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.5	(2.0, 3.0)	3.7	(3.2, 4.2)	

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.5	(2.0, 5.0)	3.7	(3.2, 4.7)	24
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Evaluation manager's discussion

The Unjournal solicited two evaluations of the paper "Water treatment and child mortality: a meta-analysis and cost-effectiveness analysis." The paper was flagged to us as important by a staff member at a major philanthropic organization, and our screening indeed suggested it could be highly influential in moving money to water treatment.

The paper does two things. It first pools evidence from many studies and so allows the authors to have the statistical precision to examine the effect of water treatment on child mortality directly. This is an improvement over past work that attempted to back out such an effect indirectly, by looking at much more common indirect signals of mortality like diarrhea.

The second thing the paper does is use the meta-analytic results to do a cost-effectiveness exercise to see how cost-effective is water treatment at avoiding death (or increasing DALYs). The main takeaway is direct estimates of water treatment show much higher reductions in mortality than do indirect methods. In turn, this means that water treatment is estimated to be much more cost-effective at averting deaths than was previously thought.

I solicited two reviews of this paper. While all the evaluators looked at the entire paper, I asked one team of evaluators to focus more on the meta-analysis and studies therein and a second evaluator to focus more on the cost-effectiveness analysis. Both evaluators agree that the paper tackles an important question and provides an advance on our prior understanding of the effects of water treatment on child mortality. Both also found areas where the paper could be improved or clarified. Our first evaluators, who worked in a team, raised many questions and helpful criticisms. These include:

1. Questions about study inclusion and exclusion and transparency.

2. Issues of data quality and analysis transparency, such as what appear to be undisclosed deviations from the pre-registration plan and changes in the odds ratios of the underlying studies between drafts.
3. Questions for scale up and policy, such as the representativeness of the sample, questions around mechanisms, and concerns around the persistence of the behavioural change.

Our second evaluation focused more heavily on the CEA model and had two major suggestions. The first was around the framing of the study. The second focused on ways to make the CEA more useful for policymakers, including:

1. Disaggregating costs to allow individual policymakers to essentially make selections off of a menu to match the CEA to their situation more closely.
2. Sensitivity analysis of the CEA, making use of the estimates of uncertainty from the meta-analysis.

The authors have responded to both evaluations and updated the working paper in response. While not all of the changes to the paper have yet been implemented, my personal reading is that the evaluators noted a number of ways that the paper could be improved, it in turn was improved, and while the headline result remains largely the same, we have now learned some new things about:

1. The stability of the results of various changes in the data
2. Additional important points in the CEA that were not clear to me up front, such as the important role of compliance in affecting the results
3. Important limitations in most existing economic research that prevents meta-analyses from being conducted or greatly limits their usefulness. In particular I'm thinking of participant flow diagrams in studies.

Anyone with an interest in this topic should read the evaluations and response in full as my summary comments contain some of my own interpretation and both the evaluators and authors may disagree with parts. A major advantage of open review is that one can read the exchange directly and form their own opinion.

I extend my sincere thanks to the evaluators and the authors for what I view as a fulfilling and transparent cooperative effort to reach the best possible answer to an important question.

Unjournal process notes

Note on versions: This working paper had two public drafts. The evaluators were recruited after the first (NBER) draft was posted online but when we learned that the authors were close to publishing a second draft we froze the process and waited for the newer draft to be published. The evaluation is of the second (May 2024) draft, though reviewers may at times make points that compare across the drafts as they read both.

Why we chose this paper

This work is very relevant to charity recommendations on water interventions. From our team notes “Kremer’s work on WASH inform[ed] Evidence Action’s \$64 million grant”. GiveWell was one of the funders of this research and they indicated a strong interest in having it evaluated. Furthermore, at least one senior academic and another senior applied researcher outside our team specifically suggested this.

For a ~nontechnical discussion, see GiveWell’s blog “[Research Strategy: Water](#)” (updated July 2024).

How we chose (and tasked) the evaluators

We selected evaluators with WASH research experience and we drew them from both the public health and development economics communities. As noted above “one team of evaluators was asked to focus more on the meta-analysis and studies therein and a second evaluator to focus more on the cost-effectiveness analysis.” The ‘team evaluation’ mode seemed particularly promising, and something we may pursue again in future evaluations.

References

1. Kremer, M., Luby, S., Maertens, R., Tan, B., & Więcek, W. (2023). Water Treatment and Child Mortality: A Meta-analysis and Cost-effectiveness Analysis. NBER Working Paper No. 30835. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w30835>

Footnotes

1.

We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

[↵](#)

2. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. [↵](#)

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4. See “1 Mar 2024 note” above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. [↵](#)

5.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

6. We have calculated a simple average across the scores, which assumes each scoring category is accorded equal weighting. ↵

7. A truly needed and useful paper. I commend the authors on what they have produced. I do not see any major technical issues with the paper. ↵

8.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↵

9. Policy decision making should be based on the results of systematic, critically appraised evidence rather than single studies, hence we agree broadly with the approach the reviewers have taken to collect and synthesize the evidence systematically. The topic of the review is highly relevant for global health policy, perhaps even more so than the reviewers indicate themselves. For example, interventions that aim to provide populations access to improved water supplies in quantity and/or quality have been shown in systematic reviews as strongly associated with reductions in diarrhoeal illness (Wolf et al., 2023), yet a systematic link to reported mortality had not been made until recently (Sharma Waddington et al., 2023). This is important since an estimated 90 percent of disability adjusted life years (DALYs) for diarrhoea are due to mortality, mainly in childhood, the remaining 10 percent being accounted for by episodes of illness across the whole population. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) estimates for water supplies are currently based on systematic reviews of morbidity, under the strong assumption that morbidity due to causes like diarrhoea is closely correlated with mortality. By collecting data from participant flow diagrams in reports of randomised controlled trials (RCTs) published in health journals, and by obtaining unpublished data on mortality from authors working in development economics and health, the reviewers provide direct estimates of mortality from water treatment and protection interventions, which can potentially be used in future GBD calculations. We also believe there is much to praise about this paper's methodological ambition to provide information for decision makers. For example, it includes cost-effectiveness analysis of various interventions, which is rarely done in meta-analyses, and employs prediction intervals to estimate the impact of a new intervention, and in this way it aims to account for heterogeneity between studies. Finally, it undertakes sensitivity analyses including estimating frequentist and Bayesian meta-analyses, together with an assessment of small study effects that finds no evidence for publication bias for mortality outcomes, which is a very rare finding in the literature on intervention effects. ↵

10. Definitely a high quality study with clear, replicable methods. As I write in my review, I think the authors could do a bit more to frame or position this study better - which speaks to how it contributes to the field. [↪](#)

11. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↪](#)

12. An important aspect of systematic reviewing is transparency in conduct and reporting, which helps to ensure the analysis can be replicated by others. The authors conducted systematic searches for published RCTs on water treatment, harvesting data on mortality that were reported in participant flow diagrams in some studies, and contacting authors of RCTs to obtain unpublished data on mortality. A previous version of the working paper omitted several trials that were included in a systematic review and meta-analysis of water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) by us, several of which have since been included in the review. In several respects, the reviewers are transparent about what they've done. For example, Fig 1 provides information about the search process and Table S2 provides information about which studies were excluded from the analysis, together with the reason why, although not in the usual form that a systematic review would provide. However, several studies of apparently eligible interventions, which reported all-cause mortality in participant flow diagrams, remain excluded from the analysis. These include Ercumen et al. (2015) which reports all-cause mortality from two trial arms (chlorine plus safe storage and safe storage alone), and Bowen et al. (2012), a long-term follow-up of another HWT study already included (Luby et al., 2006); both report higher mortality rates in the house-hold water treatment group than in the control. There are other points of inconsistency in decision-making that we noticed. For example, as noted by the authors in the supplementary materials, several study arms are of multicomponent interventions where HWT is provided alongside cookstoves and sanitation and hygiene. While it is clear how some multicomponent HWT intervention arms were assessed (e.g. Luby et al., 2018; Null et al., 2018), it is not clear how multicomponent HWT intervention arms from other studies were evaluated (e.g., Semenza et al. 1998). We were also surprised that a RCT on household water chlorination in Kenya by one of the authors (Kremer et al., 2008) was not included in the analysis or in Table S2. We understand that the working paper we have been sent to review is the second draft, the first draft being publicly circulated in 2023. We noted that the odds ratio estimates differ, in some cases considerably, between the two working paper drafts, hence we believe the authors should report inter-rater assessments on effect size data extraction and/or to indicate how discrepancies were resolved. Another key component of systematic reviewing is transparent critical appraisal of the included evidence using risk-of-bias assessment, to help the reader understand how trustworthy are the findings. The authors did conduct a risk-of-bias assessment, using a tool that was developed to assess observational studies, but the assessments are not discussed anywhere in the text or supplement, other than to indicate that all studies are RCTs and that reported mortality is an unbiased measure. As is well known, RCTs can be at 'high risk of bias' due to problems in design or conduct, an example being selection biases due to high (or highly differential) losses to follow-up (attrition) in treatment

and control arms, or late joiners in cluster-RCTs. The risk-of-bias ratings reported in the supplementary materials range between 4 and 7 out of a total possible score of 11. However, evidence suggests it is not appropriate to determine overall bias using quality scales (Jüni et al., 1999). Authors of critical appraisal tools have instead shown that it is possible to assess overall bias based on transparent decision criteria (e.g., Eldridge et al., 2019; Sterne et al., 2016). The reviewers should comment on the implications of the risk-of-bias assessment for the confidence in the findings at the review level. The authors considered the between-study heterogeneity at the review level, and predicted study effectiveness beyond the sample considered as measured by the Bayesian uncertainty analysis. However, in the Bayesian meta-analysis, the posterior estimates for individual studies differ from the frequentist model, sometimes considerably; for example, the estimate for Luby et al. (2006) shifts from a whopping OR=23.88 (95% confidence interval (CI)=0.08, 7240) to OR=0.74 (95%CI=0.37, 1.49). It would be useful for readers, who may be less familiar with Bayesian meta-analysis, if the reviewers can explain why these differences are so large. [↵](#)

13. The study executes a meta-analysis using both frequentist and Bayesian models to derive odds-ratios (OR) for reductions in child mortality from a variety of water chlorination programs. It derives a high-quality result with careful and clear inclusion of studies and an extensive sensitivity analysis. [↵](#)

14. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

15. It is standard practice in systematic reviews and meta-analyses on WASH topics to report transparently on the populations, interventions and the counterfactual water supply and sanitation conditions. It is common for WASH interventions to be implemented in conjunction with other treatments, which also may have independent or interactive effects on morbidity and mortality. This has no direct implication on the meta-analysis or on the estimation, but it might change the interpretation of the results. However, the front section of the paper does not clarify whether the studies included are standalone water treatment and protection interventions or whether they are implemented alongside other interventions. The reviewers could qualify their conclusions by observing that the results should be interpreted as approximations of the effects of “water treatment and protection”, if “water treatment and protection” interventions (in the included studies) are implemented as packages including other activities affecting morbidity and mortality. The reviewers reported an overall pooled effect together with a sub-group effect for chlorination. However, there was a potentiality for pooling effects for filtration, where there were three estimates. Perhaps the reviewers felt that the Peletz et al. (2012) study, conducted among immuno-compromised groups, was not representative of general contexts; but we note that, even if that study was excluded, meta-analytical pooling can be undertaken provided there is more than one independent effect size. It would also be useful for the reviewers to report the random effects weight of each study in the meta-analysis, as well as relative and absolute between-study heterogeneity (I-squared and Tau-squared) for all analyses conducted including sub-

groups. Having a low value of heterogeneity helps the reader understand if the pooled effect is likely to be valid within the sample of studies included in the meta-analysis. A purpose of meta-analysis is to explain the heterogeneity in estimates across studies. The reviewers conducted analysis of adherence and length of follow-up, among other factors, finding no strong association between mortality and adherence but a negative effect for follow-up length (that is, there was no significant effect for follow-ups beyond 52 weeks, as has also been found for diarrhoea morbidity). It is very difficult to measure adherence accurately since it is impossible to prevent populations from drinking other (unimproved) water sources, and because other disease transmission mechanisms may be more or less important in high-risk environments (e.g., when sanitation is classified as unimproved so most people are openly defaecating or using shared facilities that do not adequately remove excreta from the environment). On a similar note, the study does not discuss the interaction of the interventions with the baseline characteristics of the environment. The sensitivity analysis considers the baseline prevalence of diarrhoea, and the reviewers observe that the meta-analysis was not sufficiently powered to conduct a disaggregated analysis. However, the reviewers could discuss a more about how the results could differ in different contexts, since this has been a major concern in the literature. [↩](#)

16.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↩](#)

17. The review presents the numbers of deaths in treatment and control groups for all of the studies included in the meta-analysis in Table S3. This has required great effort on the part of the reviewers, and stands to be useful to researchers working on the effectiveness of interventions to reduce mortality in childhood for years to come. However, we are also concerned that the review was not reported using standards of systematic review transparency. For example, a purpose of a systematic review protocol is to enable help ensure reviewers are not making results-based choices (consciously or otherwise). This does not mean that deviations from protocol are not allowed, simply that they should be noted as such. The review was registered with the AEA registry in June 2020, but standard information reported in systematic reviews like a PRISMA study search flow diagram, or a PRISMA checklist that indicates, for example, deviations from protocol, are not given. There do appear to be deviations from the AEA registry record, such as the original exclusion of “cases where the study population is considered to be non-representative (e.g. interventions targeting HIV+ populations)” (Tan and Kremer, 2020). Yet the reviewers include a study of water filters and safe storage by Rachel Peletz and colleagues (Peletz et al., 2012) conducted among immunocompromised households. We believe that the review clearly highlights that current standards for reporting of RCTs, especially in social science, are not fit for purpose. Reputable journals publishing field trials in health require

the reporting of CONSORT participant flow diagrams, which show numbers of individual participants by study arm from recruitment of clusters and individuals within clusters, through follow-ups, together with important reasons for attrition like death in childhood (Moher et al., 1998). Without this information it is difficult to assess important threats to validity in these studies, which might occur due to problems in design and conduct. It is not sufficient to publish data openly, as many economics journals require, in order to assess them. For example, a key aspect of the internal validity in cluster-RCTs is knowledge about the point at which individual participants were recruited, so that total and differential selection bias into the study from joiners can be assessed; the same follows for selection bias out of the study (attrition), although this is more commonly evaluated. It can also be useful to know who dropped out of the study between enrolment and randomization stages to evaluate external validity. What the review demonstrates is that this lack of participant flow reporting is extremely costly. Had the participant flows been reported transparently, there would have been less need for the reviewers to contact RCT authors to obtain the attrition data on all-cause mortality in childhood - which the reviewers themselves noted was "time-consuming... and led to the loss of some data that was once available but is no longer available" (p.16) - and the ability to evaluate the credibility of the findings from the studies would be dramatically improved. RCTs are costly to undertake financially and often require substantial time engagement by participants, so there is a strong ethical and, as shown in the review, policy argument for authors to report participant flows, and for journals and commissioners to require them to do so. We also had concerns about the cost-effectiveness analysis. Firstly, the reviewers used the Bayesian meta-analysis estimate across the whole sample of studies, including filtration, spring protection and solar disinfection. However, since two of the cost-effectiveness estimates directly concern chlorination, it would seem more appropriate to use the pooled meta-analytic effects for chlorination in cost-effectiveness analysis. Secondly, sensitivity analyses to different assumptions are not reported. Finally, we believe that the positionality of the reviewers is not addressed adequately in the paper. It would be useful to know, for example, if the included RCTs conducted by the reviewers were appraised by different authors. Furthermore, one of the reviewers is a Board member of Evidence Action, the campaigning NGO that provided data on which one of the cost-effectiveness scenario estimates is based, and another is a PI of two studies that led to the organisation's earliest campaigns (Chlorination of Drinking Water and Deworm the World). We might expect these associations to be mentioned in author declarations due to the potential for conflict of interest. [↩](#)

18.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↩](#)

19. The reviewers say that "the studies included in the meta-analysis are broadly representative of the settings in which policymakers might implement water treatment programs" (p.15). It is hard to believe that

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studies could represent the contextual variability one would find within and across countries. It would be useful to understand who are the policymakers that would find this sample representative. Perhaps it should be accepted that the sample is not representative of contextual variability. But if it is representative, we suggest adding some supporting evidence of this because the argument as it stands is not very convincing. It is important to understand the different routes of infection transmission, and which particular diarrhoea-causing pathogens drinking water treatment and protection can address, in order to understand the relevance and generalisability of the findings for policy. Diarrhoea in L&MIC contexts is caused by exposure to viruses (especially rotavirus), protozoa (especially cryptosporidium) and bacteria (especially E.Coli and Shigella) (Kotloff et al., 2013). However, water treatments may not reduce faecal contamination if the treatment technology itself is not efficacious in combating parasitic infections (Arnold and Colford, 2007). An example would be chlorination which kills bacteria and most viruses – and has the advantage of providing residual protection – but, in usual doses, is ineffective against cryptosporidium, a common cause of diarrhoea in low-income contexts, especially among immunocompromised groups such as those living with HIV (Abubakar et al., 2007). Filtration, while efficacious against bacteria and larger protozoans, is less efficacious against common viruses like rotavirus, and also requires safe storage for sustained efficacy as there is no residual protection. But in order to understand generalisability of the findings from a review of behaviour change interventions, one also needs to understand if desired behaviours are practised and sustained, such as if sufficient protective agents are applied to treat drinking water or adequate personal hygiene practised at the point of use so that contaminated hands or utensils are not placed in water storage containers. One aspect of this is to assess rates of adherence and sustainability, as done by the reviewers, and discussed above. Factors causing dis-adoption include, in the case of chlorination, users disliking the odour and taste of chlorinated water. Much of the evidence on water treatment has come from RCTs conducted at zero or negligible financial costs to participants, with frequent follow-up by outsiders and disruption of normal domestic routines (the “gringo effect”), and over relatively short periods of time (Waddington et al., 2009). There is therefore a high potentiality in these studies for Hawthorne effects, where being observed leads to greater efforts to adhere to treatment protocols, favoring the treatment group in unblinded trials. This bias is especially likely to occur when follow-up and measurement occurs frequently, as it does in many household water treatment interventions. For example, in analysis that includes many of the studies used in the Kremer meta-analysis, Pickering et al. (2019: e1143) report that “virtually all the evidence that promotion of... point-of-use water treatment with chlorine or flocculent disinfectant reduce diarrhoea come from studies that had daily to fortnightly contact between the behaviour change promoter and study participant”. The findings, therefore, may be unreliable guides to the effectiveness of real-world programmes where participants are required to undertake behavioural modifications that require children’s carers always treat household drinking water while also ensuring that they never drink water from unsafe sources. ↵

20. This is my major qualm with the work. I find it a little hard to believe that policymakers—both globally, and at the national and local levels in the health sector—are unconvinced that clean water is a top choice

when allocating their funds. To this end, my suggestion to the authors is to think carefully about how they position their work and also I suggest that they improve their cost-effectiveness analysis by adding some useful sophistication to the cost model. [↵](#)

21. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

22. In theory the topic (interventions to block diarrhoeal disease transmission) and approach (systematic review and meta-analysis) are potentially highly useful for global prioritization efforts. Our major concerns were with the conduct, reporting and interpretation of the findings of the review. In addition, frequent use of the WHO GDP threshold was made, but we note that many commentators within and outside WHO have expressed their scepticism about this threshold and its use in decision-making. The GDP threshold is still widely used today, and the current study is not exceptional in this. However, since the threshold has been criticised in many ways, we suggest that the reviewers report the limitations of using the threshold for decision-making, and explain how the threshold should be interpreted for decision-making purposes in this particular context. [↵](#)

23. Yes - with some improvements as I suggest in my review. [↵](#)

24. *Top tier public health journal [↵](#)

References

1. Kremer, M., Luby, S., Maertens, R., Tan, B., & Więcek, W. (2023). *Water Treatment And Child Mortality: A Meta-Analysis And Cost-effectiveness Analysis*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w30835> [↵](#)